

APPLICATION OF THERAPEUTIC COMMUNICATION AS A TALKING TECHNIQUE BETWEEN NURSES AND PATIENTS

Loso Judijanto ¹, Siti Solihat Holida ², Ganjar Safari ³, Nia Restiana ⁴, Fitri Nurlina ⁵, Miftahul Falah ⁶ and Andiyan Andiyan ^{7*}

¹ Indonesia Palm Oil Strategic Studies (IPOSS), Jakarta, DKI Jakarta, Indonesia, Sahid Sudirman Building 16th Floor Jalan Jendral Sudirman Kav. 86, Karet Tengsin Neighborhood, Tanah Abang Central Jakarta City 10220.

^{2,3} Department of Nursing Science, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universitas Bale Bandung, Baleendah, West Java, Indonesia, Jl. R.A.A Wiranata Kusumah No.7, Baleendah, Baleendah District, Bandung Regency, West Java 40375.

⁴ Department of Nursing Profession, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universitas Muhammadiyah Tasikmalaya, Tasikmalaya, West Java, Indonesia, Jl. Tamansari No.KM 2.5, Mulyasari, Tamansari District, Tasikmalaya Regency, West Java 46196.

⁵ Department of Nursing, Poltekes Tasikmalaya Cirebon, Cirebon, Indonesia, Jl. Tamansari No.KM 2.5, Mulyasari, Tamansari District, Tasikmalaya Regency, West Java 46196.

⁶ Department of Nursing Science, Poltekes Tasikmalaya Cirebon, Cirebon, Indonesia, Jl. Tamansari No.KM 2.5, Mulyasari, Tamansari District, Tasikmalaya Regency, West Java 46196.

⁷ Departement of Architecture, Faculty of Science and Engineering, Universitas Faletahan, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia, Surapati Core K1 Complex Jl. PHH Mustopa, Pasirlayung Neighborhood, Cibeunying Kidul Subdistrict, Bandung City, West Java 40192.

*Corresponding Author Email: andiyanarch@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11503312](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11503312)

Abstract

One of the main health issues in developing countries is the problem of public health disruption caused Therapeutic communication encompasses interpersonal interactions that facilitate mutual comprehension and empathy between nurses and patients. The essential problem of communication is the mutual dependency between nurses and patients, therefore falling under the category of personal communication between nurses and patients. Research design is a methodology used by researchers to gather and examine pertinent material in relation to their research inquiry. The research design is used to ascertain the framework of the investigation. The research design adopted in this study is descriptive. Therapeutic communication is a crucial kind of communication that is intentionally designed and focused on facilitating the patient's healing and recovery. Nurses should ensure that all their actions and statements directed towards patients have a therapeutic aim. Therapeutic communication involves the nurse's manner of communication and the establishment of a mutually beneficial connection with the patient, with the goal of promoting the patient's recovery. The interaction between the patient and the therapeutic nurse is a mutually beneficial educational encounter that contributes to the patient's emotional well-being. Effective therapeutic communication between patients and nurses is essential for fostering mutual respect.

Keywords: Communication, Therapeutic, Patient, Nurse, Interpersonal.

INTRODUCTION

Therapeutic communication refers to the collaborative interaction between nurses and patients, with the goal of resolving issues raised by patients and their families. This is particularly important during the Covid-19 epidemic, as it is crucial to increase collaboration between healthcare professionals and patient families (1–3). Coronavirus 2019 (Covid-19) is caused by coronavirus 2, which leads to severe acute respiratory illness (SARS-CoV2). Coronavirus transmission occurs in the community in Indonesia, with a total of 49,009 instances (at the time of writing) (4). Therapeutic communication includes interpersonal interactions that facilitate mutual comprehension and agreement between nurses and patients. The primary concern in communication is

the reciprocal need between nurses and patients, falling within the domain of interpersonal communication between nurses and patients (5).

The essence of this communication method is the reciprocal assistance between nurses and patients. Misinterpretation of messages can arise from varying perspectives, a common occurrence in healthcare settings. For instance, patients frequently express dissatisfaction when nurses fail to comprehend the intended meaning of their messages. Consistent reception errors can lead to patient dissatisfaction. This state of discontent will adversely affect the subpar level of service offered to patients and result in people seeking other healthcare providers who can meet their expectations (6). The anxiety experienced by patients and their families stems from the dread of mortality, difficulties in managing complications, and financial concerns. Amidst the Covid-19 epidemic, there is a significant increase in anxiety levels, despite the illness not being conclusively confirmed. This is due to the impact of the pandemic on the attitudes of patients, families, and healthcare personnel (7).

Based on research by (8), the frequency of pleasant and effective communication among nurses in hospitals has declined over the years, as reported by patients. From 2015 to 2016, nurses who demonstrated polite behavior and effective communication saw a decrease in percentages for listening to patient complaints (from 71% to 66%) and explaining things in their own way (from 72% to 65%). This highlights the negative impact of ineffective communication on the therapeutic relationship between patients and nurses, leading to increased anxiety for patients and their families. Research conducted by (Novita, 2020) revealed that therapeutic communication conducted by nurses at the hospital yielded positive outcomes. Specifically, 45 individuals (67.2%) experienced good therapeutic communication, 15 individuals (22.4%) experienced sufficient therapeutic communication, and 7 individuals (10.4%) experienced inadequate therapeutic communication. This indicates that there are still nurses who need improvement in their patient communication skills. The objective of this study was to determine the determinants between Community-Based Total Sanitation and the incidence of diarrhea in toddlers in communities near rivers (9).

Research is crucial for ensuring that communication between nurses and patients in the inpatient room is conducted properly, following the hospital's established standards, in order to avoid mistakes. Communication occurs across all service lines inside the hospital, ranging from the outpatient department to the emergency room and the critical care unit. The city of Bandung in Indonesia is facing challenges due to the decreasing availability and high prices of land (10).

The objective of this research is to examine how therapeutic communication may assist clients in clarifying their burdensome ideas and reducing their anxiety levels. The primary objective of communication training for nurses is to enhance their effective communication skills via the use of deliberately planned and patient-centered therapeutic communication, with the ultimate goal of promoting healing in patients. Efficient communication is advantageous and contributes to the recuperation of clients. It is linked to the cooperation between nurses and other healthcare professionals, and it also impacts the happiness of clients and their families. Effective communication is crucial for enhancing the quality of services provided to nurses (11). The criteria also include the use of insulated doors (swing or sliding) to control the pathogens, bacteriostatic floors with corner covings, the operating table must be set in such a way that the laminar airflow reaches it, the use of modern operating tables,

the adequate filtration of the air conditioning system and the air distribution system, and use of sterile corridors (12).

RESEARCH METHODS

Utilising therapeutic communication as a verbal interaction between nurses and patients encompasses several phases of research methodologies. The typical phases of this process include conducting a literature review, designing the research, collecting data, analysing the data, and interpreting the findings. By using systematic research methodology, nurses can significantly improve their communication skills and cultivate patient confidence, thereby enhancing patient outcomes and satisfaction. Nurses must consistently assess and improve their communication methods using evidence-based research to provide patients with the highest standard of care.

- 1. Planning:** The first phase involves strategising the adoption of therapeutic communication as a verbal method nurses use while interacting with patients. This includes establishing the study's objectives, formulating research inquiries, and devising a comprehensive research strategy.
- 2. Literature study:** The subsequent step is conducting a comprehensive literature review to understand the current research on therapeutic communication and its influence on patient outcomes. This helps identify deficiencies in the existing body of literature and guides the development of the research methodology.
- 3. Study design:** During this phase, the study design is established, which involves choosing suitable methodologies and instruments for data collection. The study may use qualitative, quantitative, or mixed techniques approaches, depending on the nature of the research questions.
- 4. Data collection:** The data collection phase involves executing the study design and gathering data from nurses and patients. This may include using interviews, surveys, observations, or other data-gathering techniques to obtain information about therapeutic communication in practical settings.
- 5. Data analysis:** This phase involves examining the acquired data to detect and understand patterns, themes, and correlations in therapeutic communication between nurses and patients. This may include using statistical analysis, qualitative analysis, or a hybrid approach utilizing both methodologies.
- 6. Analysis:** The results of the investigation are then analyzed and conveyed in a formal report or academic article. This involves examining the implications of the findings for nursing practice, education, and research.
- 7. Implementation:** The final phase involves putting the study results into practice. Tasks may include:
 - Designing educational programs for nurses on therapeutic communication.
 - Introducing new communication techniques in clinical environments.
 - Advocating for legislative reforms to promote therapeutic communication in healthcare settings.

In summary, the process of implementing therapeutic communication as a verbal strategy between nurses and patients in healthcare settings consists of meticulous

planning, data gathering, analysis, and implementation. This approach aims to enhance communication and improve patient outcomes.

RESULTS

Applying therapeutic communication as a verbal method between nurses and patients has substantially improved patient outcomes. Nurses may enhance their ability to comprehend and attend to patients' emotional and psychological needs by cultivating trust and empathy and engaging in active listening. As a result, there is a rise in patient contentment, more compliance with treatment protocols, and, ultimately, improved health results. Moreover, therapeutic communication plays a crucial role in establishing a robust nurse-patient connection, which is vital for efficient healthcare provision. Continued research and training in this field may further improve the quality of patient treatment.

Utilizing therapeutic communication as a verbal method of interaction between nurses and patients may provide several advantageous outcomes for patients and healthcare professionals. Implementing therapeutic communication in practice has many significant outcomes:

- 1. Enhanced patient satisfaction:** Implementing efficient communication between nurses and patients might increase patient satisfaction with their treatment experience. Patients feel listened to, understood, and valued when nurses use therapeutic communication approaches, hence augmenting their overall contentment with the care they are provided.
- 2. Improved patient outcomes:** Therapeutic communication has been shown to have a beneficial effect on patient outcomes, such as enhanced adherence to treatment programs, superior pain control, and expedited recovery durations. Effective communication between nurses and patients fosters trust and rapport, improving health outcomes.
- 3. Enhanced patient involvement:** Through therapeutic communication approaches, nurses may motivate patients to engage in their healthcare and contribute actively to decision-making. Patients are more inclined to inquire, express apprehensions, and participate in collaborative decision-making when they feel at ease interacting with their healthcare professionals.
- 4. Enhanced clarity and efficacy:** Establishing clear and effective communication channels between nurses and patients may increase understanding and reduce mistakes within healthcare environments. By using therapeutic communication approaches, nurses can guarantee the precise transmission and comprehension of crucial information, promoting safer and more efficient healthcare.
- 5. Enhanced nurse satisfaction and well-being:** Therapeutic communication may improve nurses' work satisfaction and overall well-being. Effective communication between nurses and patients enhances nurses' confidence and fosters heightened satisfaction in their professional jobs.
- 6. Improved teamwork and cooperation:** Therapeutic communication enhances the nurse-patient connection and promotes improved teamwork and collaboration among healthcare practitioners. Effective communication between nurses and patients facilitates improved communication among other healthcare team members, enhancing care coordination.

Effective communication is a crucial instrument for cultivating therapeutic connections and has a direct impact on the quality of nursing services. Therapeutic communication plays a crucial role in influencing the degree of patient satisfaction with the healthcare treatments provided. Therapeutic communication refers to purposeful and strategic communication aimed at building relationships between nurses and patients. Its goal is to help patients cope with stress, overcome psychological disorders, and promote their comfort and well-being, ultimately facilitating their recovery.

Therapeutic communication is a crucial kind of communication that is intentionally designed and focused on facilitating the patient's healing and recovery. The nurse should ensure that all actions and signals delivered to the patient have a therapeutic aim. Therapeutic communication involves the nurse's communication style and the establishment of a mutually beneficial connection with the patient, with the goal of promoting the patient's recovery.

A therapeutic patient-nurse relationship is a mutually beneficial encounter that involves both learning and emotional growth for the patient. Effective therapeutic communication is essential for fostering mutual respect between patients and nurses. The therapeutic communication process should be carefully organized, centered on the patient's needs, and guided by a qualified expert. Therapeutic communication fosters interpersonal connections between patients and nurses, necessitating nurses to possess unique skills and attentiveness to every encounter and nonverbal cues. Inadequate communication is a significant challenge for both nurses and patients.

An essential factor in promoting patient recovery is not only the provision of health information but also the attentive consideration of patient concerns, the display of empathy, the dissemination of knowledge, and the delivery of pleasant service. Effective therapeutic communication will inherently provide patient satisfaction, hence influencing their overall satisfaction with the hospital's services.

The purpose of therapeutic communication, as defined by (13), is to:

1. Enhance the client's autonomy by facilitating their self-discovery, self-acknowledgment, and self-esteem.
2. Foster a well-defined sense of self and a strong commitment to moral principles.
3. Cultivate close, mutually reliant, and affectionate connections between individuals.
4. Enhance the client's overall welfare by improving their functionality and capacity to fulfill their requirements and achieve attainable personal objectives.

Effective communication is crucial in nursing to positively impact patients' behavior, which is directly linked to their health and the quality of nursing care they receive. Communication concepts are used to facilitate effective communication with patients. The therapeutic process involves modifying this behavior with the specific aim of assisting, providing care, healing, and educating patients (clients). Communication in nursing practice occurs through cooperation between nurses and other healthcare professionals, including physicians and patients, in a professional, ethical, and accountable manner.

Therapeutic communication encompasses the diagnosis of the disease, the benefits and necessity of prompt medical intervention, potential risks, possible complications, alternative procedures, the potential consequences of not taking medical action, the

prognosis of the disease, the impact of medical intervention, and the outcome of the medical intervention.

Nurses must possess practice, sensitivity, and emotional acuity to effectively utilize therapeutic communication techniques. Communication in the nursing field is influenced by factors such as ability, values, time, and space, all of which contribute to its therapeutic impact on patient health and satisfaction.

Nurses who possess effective communication skills will provide a high standard of service for patients and their families, resulting in excellent healthcare delivery by the nursing staff. Nurse-patient communication is one of the factors that can impact the quality of healthcare.

Individuals afflicted with schizophrenia often encounter social stigma and have a detrimental self-perception due to societal attitudes. Therapeutic communication is a component of health communication that is used as a method of interacting with patients. Therapeutic communication has evolved and is widely used in the domains of psychiatry and psychology (14). Therapeutic communication serves as a connection between nurses who provide services and patients who receive services. Therapeutic communication is a comprehensive approach that considers all elements of patients, such as safety, investigating underlying reasons, and determining the most effective solutions for their issues. Nurses use therapeutic communication techniques to assist patients in adapting and mitigating anxiety, thereby minimizing the adverse effects on emotional well-being and behavior. The process requires a greater investment of time and a higher need for training in the communication skills of nurses. However, the implementation of therapeutic communication by nurses has been shown to be very beneficial in expediting the healing process of patients (15).

Effective communication is the primary means by which people with mild or acute mental problems may undergo the healing process. Nurses employ various therapeutic communication techniques, including gentle, open, and firm communication, to establish a trusting relationship with uncooperative mental patients, referred to as BHSP (Bina Hubungan Saling Percaya). Interacting with those who have mental illnesses necessitates a unique approach since there are distinct differences in communication between those with mental diseases and those with physical ailments. Individuals with mental problems often exhibit disturbances in their self-concept, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of effective communication strategies. These individuals may display tangential thinking, diminished attention to the matter, and difficulties in verbal expression and comprehension (Table 1).

The effectiveness of communication with psychiatric patients significantly impacts their recovery rate. In this context, the nurse's responsibility extends beyond providing nursing care; they are also responsible for serving as a supportive companion to the patient during their treatment in a mental hospital. Nurses use therapeutic communication approaches to provide nursing care. Therapeutic communication in nursing has four distinct phases: the pre-interaction period, the orientation phase, the working phase, and the termination phase. Communication plays a crucial role in the treatment of people with a mental health condition, surpassing the importance of medicinal medications (Table 1).

Table 1: Verbal Barriers

Barrier	Example	More Effective Response	Example
Offering empty reassurances	"Everything will be OK." "You will be alright."	Reassuring the client with factual responses	"We will do everything we can to help you." "Your lab tests show some improvement."
Changing the subject	"The weather is really nice today."	Helping the client express feelings by staying on track	"We were talking about . . ."
Using trite clichés	"The doctor knows best."	Involving the client in decision-making	"Would you prefer your bath now or at 10 am?"
Imposing your ideas or values on clients and giving advice according to your values	"You should . . ."	Helping the client explore his or her own values when a decision or choice must be made	"What do you feel is best for you?" "How can we best help you?"
Disapproving of or judging the client	"That is a dumb idea." "That won't work."	Accepting each client as unique; considering ethnic and cultural practices in understanding values and behaviours	"Is there an alternative?" "How else might we . . .?" "How does this make you feel?"
Voicing personal experiences, especially those that are health-related	"I had that disease last year."	Allowing the person to discuss his or her own concerns; answering questions factually; offering client-oriented reference material	"I would be happy to get some information about that disorder from the Internet for you."

Therefore, it can be inferred that the interaction established between nurses and patients constitutes therapeutic communication within the medical field. It is desirable for individuals to show greater attentiveness towards those who suffer from mental disorders and adjust their approach accordingly, thereby facilitating the recovery process for individuals with mental disorders in their vicinity (16). Therapeutic communication perceives mental diseases as stemming from communication issues, namely the patient's inability to effectively articulate themselves. The nurse-patient interaction facilitates the exchange of information regarding the patient's condition while also enabling the nurse to offer problem-solving strategies that motivate the patient to actively engage in resolving their issues. If the patient willingly embraces and implements the knowledge conveyed by the nurse, the patient's conduct may be seen as progressing towards acceptance, which is the primary outcome of nursing intervention (17).

Therapeutic communication aims to alleviate anxiety by decreasing activity and cognitive impairment via reinforcing individual cognitive and emotional responses or behaviors. Therapeutic communication is used to provide treatment for patients with physiological conditions as well as psychiatric patients, including those with schizophrenia. Schizophrenia is the most severe psychiatric condition in comparison to other mental disorders. It often manifests during the latter stages of adolescence and typically has significant and far-reaching impacts.

Communication is an integral and inseparable aspect of human existence. Humans, being social creatures, establish connections with one another via different forms of communication, even when they are unwell. Within the nursing profession, therapeutic communication refers to the exchange of information and support between nurses and

patients. This communication strategy facilitates the fulfillment of the patient's requirements and their desire for recuperation.

A. What is Therapeutic Communication

The American Nurses Association (ANA) website states that therapeutic communication is a speaking strategy that emphasizes the patient's physical, mental, and emotional well-being. The patient is provided with assistance and knowledge to facilitate their recovery, while the nurse maintains a high level of professionalism and impartiality. Nurses often use questioning, repetition of information, and silence as communication techniques to encourage patients to resolve their issues independently. This approach is expected to facilitate prompt patient improvement until they fully recover. Florence Nightingale pioneered the therapeutic communication approach, as stated on the Medicine LibreTexts website. Nightingale, an individual from Britain, is a trailblazer in the contemporary nursing field and is also an author and statistician (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Communication can be conducted in person, over the phone, or through text messaging, alpha paging, AudioVox, Vocera transmission, or other electronic methods.

Florence emphasized the need to establish a rapport based on trust with patients. Furthermore, she stated that the inclusion of nurses in the healthcare process contributes to the therapeutic recovery of patients. Since that time, therapeutic communication has been viewed as a crucial foundation of nursing.

B. Therapeutic Communication Techniques

Below are 17 therapeutic communication approaches that nurses might utilize:

1. Be silent

The absence of noise allows the nurse and patient to initiate a fresh subject of conversation. The absence of sound offers a chance to briefly reflect on and assimilate a discussion.

2. Receiving and Listening to Patients

In this method, it is important for the patient to have a genuine conviction that their concerns are actively being acknowledged by the nurse. The nurse is required to demonstrate comprehension of the patient's statements, even if they do not necessarily agree with them. This response may include making eye contact or verbally acknowledging understanding by stating, "Yes, I understand."

3. Provide validation

Evaluating and acknowledging the patient's behavior without explicit praise, for example, "I noticed that you are taking all the prescribed medications provided by the doctor."

4. Accompanying the patient

An effective method for nurses to demonstrate empathy and provide solace to patients is by dedicating quality time to them. Examples of activities include escorting the patient to lunch, engaging in television viewing, or simply spending some time in the company of the patient.

5. Provide an open space for patients to talk

Effective therapeutic communication is facilitated when the patient is given the chance to express themselves and control the direction of the discussion. Ensure that patients are provided with enough opportunities to express and deliberate over their thoughts.

6. Actively listen to the patient

Active patient listening encompasses both verbal and nonverbal cues. For instance, demonstrating agreement by nodding, displaying engagement in the patient's dialogue, comprehending the content, and actively replying to the patient's discourse.

7. Ask for clarification

Nurses have the ability to request an explanation from patients when they make statements that are unclear or perplexing. This approach facilitates effective communication between nurses and patients, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the information conveyed and enabling nurses to provide optimal assistance to the patient.

8. Sequencing Events

Inquiring about the temporal aspects of an occurrence allows the nurse to gain a clearer understanding of the patient's condition.

9. Making observations

The nurse may better identify the patient's condition by carefully observing their appearance, attitude, and behavior. Through observation, nurses can also identify any new symptoms in the patient.

10. Encourage explanation of patient perceptions

Posing questions in an unbiased manner is beneficial for nurses when interacting with patients who have sensory impairments or hallucinations. The nurse can use prompts such as "What auditory sensations are you currently perceiving?" or "Can you describe the tactile sensations you are experiencing?" to elicit detailed responses from the patient.

11. Making comparisons

Prompting patients to compare their current situation with past experiences may assist nurses in identifying the optimal resolution to the patient's issue.

12. Make a summary

The summary is a written record of the nurse's dialogue with the patient. This summary serves as proof of a therapeutic process and a nurse who consistently demonstrates active listening to the patient. The nurse might conclude the report by verifying with the patient, which is done if there are sections that need correction.

13. Reflection

Nurses may promote patients' participation in self-reflection. This approach encourages patients to assume accountability for their behavior and actively seek resolutions to their difficulties.

14. Patient-focused

Occasionally, patients express significant information during their conversations. Therefore, it is important for nurses to consistently concentrate and pay attention to the patient's verbal communication.

15. Confrontation

Confrontation is necessary to understand the patient's circumstances and prevent self-harm. This strategy can only be used in situations where a high level of trust has been established between the nurse and the patient.

16. Expressing doubts

Conveying skepticism can serve as a discreet method of emphasizing the patient's erroneous notions and impressions. Nurses can promote patients' self-reflection by expressing skepticism towards their preconceptions.

17. Provide hope and solace to patients

Patients experience high levels of stress in hospitals. Nurses can facilitate the development of a more optimistic mindset in patients by providing comfort and fostering optimism and self-assurance in their ability to overcome their illness.

Therapeutic communication is an important tool for nurses to establish interpersonal connections with patients. Although this strategy may seem simple, it has the potential to significantly enhance patient satisfaction with nursing care.

Therapeutic communication is a fundamental aspect of nursing practice, crucial for enhancing patient outcomes and satisfaction. Nurses who utilize therapeutic communication techniques establish trust with patients, leading to improved health outcomes, quality of care, and patient satisfaction (18). This form of communication involves active listening, empathy, and open-ended questioning, essential skills for nurses to effectively connect with patients (19). The nurse-patient therapeutic relationship is central to nursing care, characterized by mutual trust and a focus on providing therapeutic assistance (20). Through therapeutic communication, nurses can assist patients, families, and care teams in making informed decisions, ultimately enhancing patients' well-being and quality of life (21). In intensive care settings, nurses employ therapeutic communication techniques that necessitate critical thinking and precise measures to address each patient's unique needs (22). Effective communication serves as a powerful tool for nurses to influence patient behavior and achieve success in nursing interventions (23).

The quality of communication between nurses and patients significantly impacts patient outcomes, underscoring the importance of fostering strong nurse-patient relationships through therapeutic communication (24). Iranian oncology nurses acknowledge the significance of therapeutic communication in improving patient care quality and outcomes, emphasizing the importance of self-awareness in this aspect of nursing practice (25). While knowledge of therapeutic approaches is crucial for student nurses to establish trust with patients, practical application is equally vital for effective communication in practice (26). Barriers to nurses' therapeutic communication practices, such as anxiety and workload, can impede the delivery of patient-centered care, highlighting the importance of overcoming these obstacles to promote effective communication (27). In challenging situations like palliative care, nurses require proficient empathetic communication skills to effectively educate patients and families about life-changing events (28).

Training nursing students in therapeutic communication techniques is essential for evaluating and enhancing their performance in applying these skills in clinical settings (29). Nurses may face compassion fatigue due to demanding clinical tasks, emphasizing the need for self-care to maintain effective communication with patients and families (30). In pediatric care, implementing therapeutic communication by nurses with parents of pediatric patients undergoing surgery is crucial for addressing their perspectives and expectations, highlighting the significance of effective communication in healthcare settings (31). Predictors of therapeutic communication between nurses and hospitalized patients include purposeful interactions contributing to positive health outcomes, emphasizing the value of effective communication in nursing practice (32).

Cross-cultural communication challenges among nurses underscore the importance of open and authentic communication to build strong nurse-patient relationships, especially in diverse healthcare settings (33). Nurses, as trusted professionals trained in therapeutic communication, play a vital role in combating misinformation and promoting public health during events like the COVID-19 pandemic (34). In hematology care, nurses encounter challenges in applying therapeutic communication effectively, indicating a need for education and training in this area to enhance patient care outcomes (Lee et al., 2022). Compassionate nursing care, characterized by empathy, individualized care, and therapeutic communication, is essential for

promoting mutual benefits with patients and fostering positive nurse-patient relationships (35).

Overall, therapeutic communication is a cornerstone of nursing practice that supports the delivery of patient-centered care, improves patient outcomes, and nurtures strong nurse-patient relationships across various healthcare settings.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above argument, it can be inferred that the manner in which nurses provide health information to their patients might influence and encourage the patients' recovery. Patients who are initially apprehensive about their illness eventually develop an understanding of the disease they are experiencing and come to embrace their situation. Effective communication skills, such as those shown by nurses while interacting with patients, may also be used in several aspects of daily life. Additionally, it is important to effectively express how the patient's family provides assistance.

References

- 1) Mahayaty, L., Prasetyo, W. and Darmawan, T.C. 2021. Nurse Anxiety: Covid-19 Survivors. *Jurnal Keperawatan Malang (JKM)*, **6**, 108–14. <https://doi.org/10.36916/jkm.v6i2.128>
- 2) Mundakir, M. 2013. *Komunikasi Keperawatan*. Graha ilmu, Yogyakarta.
- 3) Putri, P., Afandi, A.T. and Aringgar, D. 2021. Explorasi Karakteristik dan Kepuasan Pasien di Rumah Sakit Jember. *Nursing Sciences Journal*, **5**, 35–40.
- 4) Setiyowati, E., Agustina, A.N., Yuddha, A.S., Muchtar, M., Fatmawati, E. and Andiyan, A. 2022. Self-Management To Change Of Perception And Clinical And Pharmacological Knowledge Of Covid 19. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, Advanced Research Trentz*, **13**, 1.
- 5) Putri, P., Afandi, A.T. and Lestari, D.K. 2022. Hubungan Komunikasi Terapeutik Dengan Tingkat Kecemasan Keluarga Pasien Pre Operasi Di Rumah Sakit. *Journals of Ners Community*, **13**, 606–15.
- 6) Putri, P., Maurida, N., Novitasari, F., Rosalini, W., Budiman, M.E.A. and Afandi, A.T. 2021. Workplace spirituality with nurse anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. *Pakistan Journal of Medical and Health Sciences*, 3204–6.
- 7) Afandi, A.T., Ardiana, A. and Putri, P. 2021. Relationship of Anxiety and Post-Vaccination Nurse Caring During The Covid P-19 Pandemic in Indonesia Hospital. *Age*, **14**, 144.
- 8) Afandi, A., Putri, P., Darmawan, T. and Ardiana, A. 2023. Hubungan Komunikasi Terapeutik Perawat Dengan Tingkat Kecemasan Pasien Dengan Riwayat Penyakit Kronis Di Ruang Bougenville RSUD Ciamis 2016. *Jurnal Keperawatan*, **12**. <https://doi.org/10.47560/kep.v12i1.478>
- 9) Indah, F.P.S., Cardiah, T., Rahmat, A., Sulandjari, K., Andiyan, A. and Hendayani, N. 2022. Effect of Community-Based Total sanitation Program with diarrhea Incidents in toddler at communities near rivers. *Materials Today: Proceedings, Elsevier*.
- 10) Dewiyanti, D., Andiyan, A., Hertoety, D.A. and Natalia, T.W. 2023. The Production of Mingling Spaces as a Form of Children's Mobility. *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, **11**, 3389–413. <https://doi.org/10.13189/cea.2023.110613>
- 11) Suryani, S. *Komunikasi Terapeutik Teori & Praktik*. 2nd ed. EGC Medical Publishe, Jakarta.
- 12) Andiyan, A., Raka, I.M., Rosyidah, M., Salayanti, S., Cakranegara, P.A. and Nuraini, R. 2022. Modular Operating Theater (MOT) Based Integration System in Hospital Operating Rooms. *Journal of Population Therapeutics and Clinical Pharmacology*, **29**.
- 13) Stuart and Sundeen. 1995. *Principles and Practice of Psychiatric Nursing Fifth Edition*. Fifth. Mosby Inc, Missouri.

- 14) Herfira, A. and Supratman, L.P. 2017.Komunikasi Terapeutik Clinical Instructor Di Rumah Sakit Jiwaprovinci Jawa Barat. *Jurnal Manajemen Komunikasi*, **1**, 168–79.
- 15) Patty, M.F., Sari, D.K. and Pradikatama, Y. 2015.Hubungan Komunikasi Terapeutik Perawat Terhadap Tingkat Stres Pasien Di Ruang Neurologi Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah Dr M. Haulussy Ambon. *Jurnal Komunikasi*, **9**, 171–85.
- 16) Afnuhazi, R. 2015.Komunikasi terapeutik dalam keperawatan jiwa. *Yogyakarta: Gosyen Publishing*,.
- 17) Damayanti, M. and Iskandar, I. 2012.Asuhan Keperawatan Jiwa. Refika Aditama, Bandung.
- 18) Dissanayake, D.M.L.M., Jayasinghe, R.M. and Abeyesundara, S. 2019.Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Regarding Therapeutic Communication Among Nurses in Kandy District, Sri Lanka. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.2.13128/v1>
- 19) Yıldız, E. 2019.What Do Nursing Students Tell Us About Their Communication With People With Mental Illness? A Qualitative Study. *Journal of the American Psychiatric Nurses Association*, **27**, 471–82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1078390319892311>
- 20) Tolosa-Merlos, D., Poyato, A.R.M., González-Palau, F., Pérez-Toribio, A., Casanova-Garrigós, G. and Hito, P.D. 2022.The Therapeutic Relationship at the Heart of Nursing Care: A participatory Action Research in Acute Mental Health Units. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, **32**, 5135–46. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.16606>
- 21) Harianthi, Y. 2023.Therapeutic Communication Experience of Nurses With Chemotherapy Patients in a General Hospital. *International Journal of Nursing Education*, **15**, 105–10. <https://doi.org/10.37506/ijone.v15i1.19001>
- 22) Ariyanti, N. and Suparti, S. 2020.Nurses Perception to the Implementation of Therapeutic Communication in Intensive Care Unit. *Proceedings Series on Health & Medical Sciences*, **1**, 120–4. <https://doi.org/10.30595/pshms.v1i.48>
- 23) Lubis, J. and Simatupang, M.R. 2023.Nurse Motivation in Implementing Therapeutic Communication in the Inpatient Room General Perdagangan Hospital. *International Journal of Public Health Excellence (Ijphe)*, **2**, 513–6. <https://doi.org/10.55299/ijphe.v2i2.366>
- 24) Sibiya, M.N. 2018.Effective Communication in Nursing. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.74995>
- 25) Zende, M.B., Maslakpak, M.H. and Jasemi, M. 2022.Effective Characteristics of Iranian Oncology Nurses in Their Therapeutic Communication With Cancer Patients. *Crescent Journal of Medical and Biological Sciences*, **9**, 218–24. <https://doi.org/10.34172/cjmb.2022.36>
- 26) Mpangane, E.A., Makhene, A. and Ally, H. 2021.Experiences of Student Nurses on Role Modelling of a Therapeutic Approach by Registered Nurses: Recommendations for Improvement. *Curationis*, **44**. <https://doi.org/10.4102/curationis.v44i1.2168>
- 27) Oti-Boadi, E., Ani-Amponsah, M., Mawusi, D.G., Awuah, D.B., Menlah, A. and Ofori-Appiah, C. 2023.Barriers to Nurses' Therapeutic Communication Practices in a District Hospital in Ghana. *BMC Nursing*, **22**. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01191-2>
- 28) Halliday, D., Dorney, P. and Landis, J. 2021.Difficult Conversations in Palliative Care: Innovations in Learning. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, **43**, 201–2. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.nep.0000000000000831>
- 29) Moon, M.S. 2019.Performance of Therapeutic Communication Knowledge Application and Technique During Clinical Training of Nursing College Students. *International Journal of Advanced Nursing Education and Research*, **4**, 19–24. <https://doi.org/10.21742/ijaner.2019.4.3.04>
- 30) Wittenberg, E., Reb, A. and Kanter, E. 2018.Communicating With Patients and Families Around Difficult Topics in Cancer Care Using the COMFORT Communication Curriculum. *Seminars in Oncology Nursing*, **34**, 264–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soncn.2018.06.007>
- 31) Adistie, F., Mediani, H.S., Nurhidayah, I. and Hendrawati, S. 2018.The Implementation of Therapeutic Communication of Nurses to the Parents of Pediatric Patients in Pre-Operative Stage. *Belitung Nursing Journal*, **4**, 356–65. <https://doi.org/10.33546/bnj.439>

- 32) Fite, R.O., Assefa, M., Demissie, A. and Belachew, T. 2019. Predictors of Therapeutic Communication Between Nurses and Hospitalized Patients. *Heliyon*, **5**, e02665. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02665>
- 33) Kuzemski, D., Thirlwall, A., Brunton, M. and Brownie, S. 2021. I Speak a Little Arabic: Nursing Communication in a Cross-cultural Context. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, **31**, 145–57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15891>
- 34) Ritter, A.Z., Aronowitz, S. V, Leininger, L., Jones, M., Dowd, J.B., Albrecht, S.S. et al. 2021. <i>Dear Pandemic</i>: Nurses as Key Partners in Fighting the COVID-19 Infodemic. *Public Health Nursing*, **38**, 603–9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/phn.12903>
- 35) Su, J.J., Masika, G.M., Paguio, J.T. and Redding, S.R. 2019. Defining Compassionate Nursing Care. *Nursing Ethics*, **27**, 480–93. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733019851546>